

<https://doi.org/10.48047/AFJBS.6.14.2024.7285-7298>

African Journal of Biological Sciences

Journal homepage: <http://www.afjbs.com>

Research Paper

Open Access

Evaluation of Resource Management as a Marketing Strategy in Hotel Industry: with Reference to Heritage Hotels of Jaipur

Mandeep Kumar¹, Dr. Deep Kumar Mathur², Dr. T. K Jain³, Dr. Leena Sharma⁴, Dr. Manish Shrivastava⁵, Dr. Praveen Kumar Sharma⁶

Research Scholar, School of Hotel Management, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur¹
Orchid id : 0009-0005-9833-1178

Associate Professor, International School of Business Management, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur²

Dean, International School of Business Management, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur³

Head of Department, Assistant Professor, Department of Business Administration, St. Xavier's College, Jaipur⁴

Principal, School of Hotel Management, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur⁵

Assistant Professor, School of Hotel Management, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur⁶

Corresponding Author: mandeep.0000@gmail.com

Volume 6, Issue 14, Aug 2024

Received: 15 June 2024

Accepted: 25 July 2024

Published: 15 Aug 2024

[doi: 10.48047/AFJBS.6.14.2024.7285-7298](https://doi.org/10.48047/AFJBS.6.14.2024.7285-7298)

Abstract

Heritage hotels are generally the old palaces, Forts and related buildings that are converted into hotels by the owners, even in some of the cases new buildings are raised with all the heritage amenities and feel. Guests visiting these hotels use to experience the royal treatment with all the modern facilities included. This present study evaluates the management of resources as a key factor for the development of selected heritage hotels in Jaipur. The focus will be on the resources like employees, logistics, maintenance and other related factors responsible to maintain the competitiveness of these hotels. This study is based on primary data and the Likert Scale based questionnaire is prepared to collect the data. Location of the study was Jaipur, Rajasthan.

Keywords: Strategy, Tourism, Hotel Industry, Heritage Hotels.

Introduction

Heritage hotels are the part and parcel of tourism industry all over the world, considering India as a destination; Rajasthan can be stated as the most heritage rich state. The heritage hotels of Rajasthan are popular all over the world and tourist use to visit here specially for the feel this heritage. For international tourists, heritage hotels of Rajasthan have remained a lucrative destination, they want to stay in these hotels to get the royal feeling and treatment, culinary cuisines, furniture and fixtures of ornamental value and many other related aspects. Prior to 1991 i.e. before the announcement of Industrial Policy, 1991 only a few heritage hotels in Rajasthan, but in the later years the gates of international commerce and trade were opened for Indian hotel industry, considering this the owners of royal palaces, forts, havelis, etc. started to convert their properties in heritage hotels. There were wo benefits of the same; firstly, they were able to maintain their huge properties that were going in vain, secondly, they started to get great revenue on these spare properties.

For last 20 years i.e., 2002 to 2022 high growth and potential has been identified in this segment of hotel industry and owners of heritage hotels in Rajasthan are required tap this potential and meet the demand generated via this process. The contribution of hotel industry in the growth of Indian economy is tremendous and to add more stars in the crown it becomes very crucial to study the drivers for success in this sector. This present study on management of resources in heritage hotels carries a great relevance in such a scenario. The boom in India's tourism industry and the surge in tourist inflow to the country have percolated to other associated sectors like handicrafts, aviation, destination specific tourism, night outs, etc.

Since the initial years of 21st century, Rajasthan is experiencing an exponential growth in hospitality and hotel industry. It can be viewed in the areas of increased occupancy ratio, hike in the price of rooms (on average), coming up of new heritage places, etc. As per the report of **FICCI (2017)** the number of hotel rooms across the country were around 1 lac in 2005 and raised to approximately 3 lacs in 2015, this includes the existing heritage hotels and the other related projects coming up. Hence, the demand is increasing on exponential level, and in order to get the bigger piece of the pie it is important to keep up with the pace. But it has been established in many of the previous studies that in terms of heritage hotels, services are required to be provided has not changed, albeit technological advancements are embraced by the industry. Though thanks to the service providing apps and websites i.e. make my trip, Thomos cook, etc.

as these platforms have boosted the technological front of the hotel industry in Rajasthan with that of the country. Even most of the heritage hotels are having their own websites where the customers can visit and process their bookings and related travel plans, this system has provided a boost to the overall business and made the system easier for all the stakeholder. Apart from this the technological advancements the chances of fraudulent activities have minimized and people feel more secure and safe in terms of their travel plans and stay in the heritage places.

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/724631/revpar-of-hotels-in-jaipur-india/>

Figure 1: Revenue per available hotel room across Jaipur in India from financial year 2010 to 2022

It is crucial for the heritage hotels that all the guests visiting their avenues must be satisfied from all the aspects like the ambience, treatment, service, facilities, individual attention, etc. such facilities and amenities are liable to be anticipated in advance and this will certainly ensure the satisfaction of the guests and revisit as well. Addressing the complaints of customer can be another important component for the heritage hotels. As in everything preventing complaints is better than dealing with them. Tourists expect the convenience of a hotel pick up for their day tours while wanting to taste the local cuisines. Business travelers expect quick and efficient

service, good internet speed and Wi-Fi, complimentary breakfast/lunch among others. It is very relevant and is a 'must do' kind of task for the hotels, although this is essential for the hotels but then again quality of these services may add value to the hotel.

Hotel industry is a customer centric service and it takes a lot of effort to maintain a brand for it in the market, in the present scenario branding is very important even for the heritage hotel industry. This ensures the responsibility of the hotels that their customers get the best of the values. Here the role of hospitality manager and related staff becomes crucial as they are the frontliners to face the customers in all respects and carry the image of hotel as well. They must ensure that customers feel welcomed, courteously and efficiently served in a clean, safe and secured environment with the best quality of products sold at a reasonable price. It is more crucial in case of heritage hotel industry. If the management of resources is not done properly then the image of the hotel will be diluted, this can be done by following the national and international standards of hospitality industry. Tourists may not find it worthwhile to come all the way just for a tour. An innovative mechanism to streamline this development can be to market a heritage tourism destination as an alternative tourism destination. Hence, Management of resources associated with them is very much needed. Many of the national and international heritage hotels are maintaining commendable line of standards and these standards are benchmark for others. In a number of cases, only following the standards is not enough i.e. ongoing processes of the hotels should also be in line, like the resources available at the hotel, their management and qualitative usage of the resources. These resources can be human resources, materialistic resources, resources of physical appearance, etc. if any of the resource deplete or misused then it will be negative on the processes of the hotel and even on the image of the hotel.

Rai (2019) stated that hotel industry is basically customer centric and important for the hotels to focus on the comfort and facilitation of their guests, as a matter of fact this is not an easy task but can be managed generously based on the available resources. As far as heritage hotels are concerned customers use to incur large amount of money to stay in the hotel and take the experience of royal treatment till their stay in the hotel, in this way they get maximum value of their money. It is the duty of hotel staff that the visitors get satisfied in all respects and should feel welcomed, any variation in the hospitality can reduce the chances that the customer will revisit the hotel in near future. This can be done with the help of all the available resources i.e. all

the resources should be deployed in right direction. Any lack in the management of resources can harm the business and image of the hotel in long term. **Dinkar (2020)** stated that a proper and long-term mechanism should be in place for development of destination itself and the other logistics related concerns. Resources are having strategic value and in case of heritage hotels they use to play a more vital role because such hotels can be developed as of alternate tourist destination, which means higher revenue for the industry and even for the state.

Hence, Management of resources is very important for all the heritage hotels in the country including state of Rajasthan. On the other hand, it is very important to maintain continuum between supply of resources and usage of the same, because if the balance is not maintained then the scarcity of resources may occur and this scarcity can diminish the working of the hotels along with the image of the same.

Literature Review

Bagri et al. (2015) Concentrated on the influence of employees for guest satisfaction, the researcher stated that on certain fronts it was found that a dissatisfied employee may not be enthusiast enough to cater the employees with good mood. Better policies and programs for employees may increase the morale of the employees. If the employees get motivated then they will share a good image of the organization with the hotel guests. The researcher also viewed this aspect as the tool of marketing and increasing the competency of the hotel for growth and economic development. The researcher emphasized on the importance of human resource in hotel industry, no doubt that human resource is very important for the organization but then again dissatisfied human resource can be serious concern for any give organization. Training of the human resource, right placement and right remuneration can motivate the employees; this is important for the organization, then again it is very important that the organizations should deploy the human resources very carefully and patiently. The researcher also stated that the qualification and experience of the human resource is very important as the right person in right place can give the desired results, also the staff members carry the image of the hotel and are liable to present in front of the guests staying in the hotel.

Banu (2017) worked on the sustainability of the environment and role of heritage hotels in the same. He stated that inculcation of the sustainability related practices and promotion of the same

on all the available platforms can increase the competency of the heritage hotels among the prospective visitors and a good image of the hotel will be shared in the open market. This can also be viewed as strategic tool meet the market competition. Sustainability is a very strong and affirmative component as far as hotel industry is concerned, in the present times water harvesting, Go Green, environment protection, safety & security, information collection & processing, etc. are found to be closely related with the dimension of sustainability, however heritage hotels are following most of the sustainability related components but then again many of such components are found only in papers and not in practice. The researcher also stated that the flow of sustainability is only possible with the help of right kind of resources in right place. Pushing the level of sustainability requires attention of the management and deployment of available resources at the right time and right place. Many of the star hotels, apart from the heritage hotels, are religiously engaged in the drive of sustainable development and also engaging their resources in this direction.

Ambardar (2018) the study entails that resources are crucial for the development of heritage hotels, important resources are human resource, materials, logistics, ambience, presence of physical components i.e., furniture, fixtures, decoration, etc. and many other related items. Obviously, these components are costly and may be of recurring nature but then again proper maintenance of such resources can increase the value of heritage hotels for all the stakeholders, including customers. Apparently, they can also be used as tools for the strategic framework required for marketing of the heritage hotels. Here it is important to mention that resources can be useful for strategy formulation on collective basis i.e. promotion or usage of one or few resources can not be sufficient enough to frame a suitable strategy. However, the strategy for the usage and application of resource may be deployed in coordination with the management and the people who are going to use them i.e., the support or the ground staff of hotel.

Bhatia (2017) this study states that the government agencies are capable of analyzing the scenario of Indian tourism industry and can find the most suitable opportunities and minimize the forthcoming threats in order to benefit the overall industry. The study also stated that the global trends in the tourism industry will be facing a major turmoil in the times to come, this shift will be related to the visit of foreign tourist in the country and the respective economic benefits out of

the same. Now the government agencies are liable to tap this opportunity and get the maximum benefit out of the same, the preparations are related to the development of basic infrastructure and providing of facilities to the guests. It is not an easy task but then again India is ready to welcome this new and vibrant wave of tourists in the country. Specially the heritage hotels are waving the flags of integration and historical connections with vibrant colors of the nation and even the international frontiers. In such scenario available resources of the hotels are crucial role in terms of ambience, artifacts, presence of physical components, etc.

Kalaskar (2013) tourism and travel have remained the important components of the Indian society since the pre-historic period, this practice has increased in the recent times and with the introduction of information technology have provided wings to this process by the end of 20th century. Heritage hotels are not only known for their royal ambience but also for the duration they are operating and contributed to the economy as such. In the 21st century they have become the integral part of the tourism industry and contributing to the economic growth of the country including Rajasthan. Right kind of marketing strategy is certainly going to provide boost to such heritage hotels. The researcher also mentioned the smart use of resources available with the hotels (Heritage and normal), as these resources can add value to the hotel as well.

Objective of the Study

Major objective of the study is to assess the importance of resources required for the growth of heritage hotels in Rajasthan and its importance in framing right kind of marketing strategy for the same.

Hypothesis

H₀: The materialistic and human resources are having significant role in the development of appropriate marketing strategy for Heritage hotels.

H₀: The materialistic and human resources are not having significant role in the development of appropriate marketing strategy for Heritage hotels.

Research Methodology

This study is based on primary data and the respondents were the hospitality managers, floor mangers, senior managers, etc. working the selected heritage hotels for at least two years.

Duration of the study was from March 2023 to May 2023. Purposive sampling is being used for this present study as responsive sample units are not confirmed i.e., they will participate in the survey or not. A total of 120 officials were contacted for the study. The selected hotels are mentioned below:

S. No.	Name of Selected Hotel
1	Raj Palace (Built: 1727)
2	Jai Mahal (Built: 1745)
3	Rambagh Palace (Built: 1835)
4	Samode Haveli (Built: 1900)
5	Narain Niwas Palace (Built: 1928)

The time lap of the origin of above said hotels ranges from 17th to 20th century, some of the heritage hotels are being converted from old palaces and forts, many hotels are being raised in the form of a heritage place i.e. the ambience of the hotel is comparable to the standard heritage hotels. After independence when the act of 1935 came into action and most of the owners were not able to maintain the royal lifestyle or take care of the palaces and forts owned by their ancestors, gradually they got converted in hotels and wedding destinations. In final years of 20th century some palaces and forts were taken over by government and declared monuments, in the later years they were opened for public and this enabled the agencies to maintain such buildings. Palaces and forts converted into hotels became famous and got the attention of foreign tourists and rich families in the country. In a gradual succession all such hotels became the integral part of national tourism industry and started to generate revenue at the state and national level.

A detailed questionnaire having open-ended and 5-point Likert scale-based questions was exercised face to face with the respondents. **Manish et al (2012); Sharma et al (2022); Dwivedi et al (2010)**. Other than the primary data a researcher consulted the detailed secondary data from various sources has also been followed to prepare the background, objectives and hypothesis of the study. Different statistical tools like, mean, Standard deviation and skewness were used to analyze the data, all the analysis is presented in the form of charts. ANOVA-test One way was

used to analyze the data and PH-STAT 2 is applied to code the data. As a matter of fact, the ANOVA test is being used find the variance among the responses of the selected sample units, in this present study also the researcher has tried find the variance and normalize the results with the said objectives and assessment of the stated hypothesis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Summary of ANOVA Test Results

On the basis of Experience	F	Sig.
Shortage of resources create functional difficulties	2.082	2.016
Recurring cost on materials can improve the image	.534	.711
Employees are the face of hotel	.983	1.817
Logistics related resources are on time	1.885	1.712
Materials of physical presence create an image	1.117	1.348
Cuisines are valuable for the heritage hotels	1.443	1.519
Guests of heritage hotels look forward to royal treatment	.445	1.017
Service-related resources very important	.316	.814
Outsourced material resources are important	5.324	7.992
Scarcity of resources may harm image of hotel	2.371	2.310
On the basis of Shifts		
Shortage of resources create functional difficulties	.209	.890
Recurring cost on materials can improve the image	.579	.629
Employees are the face of hotel	.993	1.396
Logistics related resources are on time	.593	.620
Materials of physical presence create an image	.456	.503
Cuisines are valuable for the heritage hotels	1.111	.344
Guests of heritage hotels look forward to royal treatment	3.445	3.112
Service-related resources very important	.316	.414
Outsourced material resources are important	1.091	1.822
Scarcity of resources may harm image of hotel	2.371	2.070
On the basis of employment in current Hotel		
Shortage of resources create functional difficulties	1.133	1.935
Recurring cost on materials can improve the image	1.297	1.820
Employees are the face of hotel	2.005	2.002
Logistics related resources are on time	.033	1.902
Materials of physical presence create an image	.684	1.652

Cuisines are valuable for the heritage hotels	2.336	2.547
Guests of heritage hotels look forward to royal treatment	.012	.911
Service-related resources very important	.599	1.439
Outsourced material resources are important	.407	.524
Scarcity of resources may harm image of hotel	.003	.959
On the basis of Income		
Shortage of resources create functional difficulties	.082	.970
Recurring cost on materials can improve the image	.360	.782
Employees are the face of hotel	1.355	2.256
Logistics related resources are on time	1.524	1.507
Materials of physical presence create an image	.660	.777
Cuisines are valuable for the heritage hotels	.823	1.481
Guests of heritage hotels look forward to royal treatment	1.126	.338
Service-related resources very important	1.301	1.425
Outsourced material resources are important	1.056	1.367
Scarcity of resources may harm image of hotel	1.398	1.242

Interpretation

The researcher had applied ANOVA (One way) to analyze the data, the thumb rule that applies here is 'if the Sign. (Significance value) values are higher than the values of F (F-Ratio) then the hypothesis is accepted or else rejected.'

Selected components choose on the basis of evaluation (Dependent Variables):

- Total Experience of respondents
- Working Shift of Respondents
- Employment in current hotel of Respondents
- Income of Respondents

As can be seen from the above table of analysis and results of ANOVA test, it can be stated that on the basis of total experience of the selected sample units the amount of variation is less, this shows that many respondents were agreed to the point in question and believe that human and materialistic resources are crucial for the heritage hotels as these resources use to present the image of the hotel in the minds of customers and even in the market. Most of the respondents stated that physical ambience and royal treatment are the main concern of foreign tourists. As far as cuisines are concerned these are being appreciated by the guest but then again it is a matter of taste and may be there lies some variation on the basis of liking and disliking.

Selected staff members use to work in shifts, here it is important to mention that the staff members working in day shift have different thought process from those who use to in night shift. In the day shift, generally there is a rush of guests and all the guests are having pre-booking in the hotels; only lodging is left, apparently it becomes crucial for the day staff to present a good image for guests, here service plays a very crucial role. Then in night shift the ambience changes where the physical presence of the ambience plays its role, like lighting in rooms and premises of the hotel, bonfire, dinner, presentation of local cuisines, etc. rather in both type of staff, level of variation is not much to reject the hypothesis.

Employees those who have joined the selected heritage hotel in recent times are still in learning phase and trying to cope up with the concept of heritage hotels, this is the reason that here the amount of variation is high among the variation of respondents, but then again, the Sign. value is higher in most of the cases. This has been accepted by the newly joined staff members that the human and materialistic resources are crucial for the image of the hotel and important tool in framing the marketing strategy in future terms.

Result

On the basis of above analysis, it can be stated that the selected staff members were agreed to the point in question that human and materialistic resources are crucial for the growth of heritage hotels. Even such resources play important role in framing the marketing strategy for the heritage hotels. Hence the null hypothesis '*The materialistic and human resources are having significant role in the development of appropriate marketing strategy for Heritage hotels.*' Can be accepted and the alternate hypothesis can be rejected. It was also observed in the process of research that

the heritage hotels in Jaipur and near by cities are using their resources very carefully and smartly. In most of the cases, management is maintaining proper continuum between supply and usage of these resources. This chain of resource handling is the integral part of sustainable development and this sustainable development is very important according the reports of government and private agencies. Although in few cases relevance between the usage and application of resources couldn't be found, this may be because of the reason that heritage hotels are converted from old palaces & forts and in the process of this conversion some amount of relevance may be lost due to heritage value of the fixed type of resources.

Conclusion

This study has identified the need for research that could improve the understanding of heritage tourism and use of resources as a tool of marketing strategies. These researches have highlighted some important managerial implications and find out that heritage matters. On the other hand, resources available with the heritage hotels are generally common, but the difference lies in the orientation and appearances of the same. The study has included middle level and front-line staff in the study, as they are in closest encounter with the guests visiting heritage hotels and only, they can give the most authentic review on the availability and application of resources. The finding of the study stated that most of the respondents gave importance to the human and materialistic resources and stated that cuisines are also very important but they are the matter of taste and preference of customer, hence the difference may lie in liking and disliking of the same. Then on a cumulative basis all the selected respondents have almost the same opinion for the human and materialistic resources. It is true and is being realized in the number of previous studies that guests use to get attracted by the ambience and facilities available at any given hotel but in case of heritage hotels this becomes even more important because the re-visit of the respective guests is important i.e. the business of the heritage hotels depends on the satisfaction of guests, it can be said that this satisfaction is majorly dependent on the service related resources and other related resources that are having physical presence. If the management of such resources is well designed and organized, satisfaction level of the guests is increased and they will certainly recommend the services to other guests also. Along with the feedback of guests it is very important for the hotels to maintain continuum between supply of resources and usage of the same, because if the balance is not maintained then the scarcity of resources may occur and this scarcity can diminish the working of the hotels along with the image of the same.

References

1. Ahmad T., Dr. Jawabreh O., Afeef M., Almomani A. (2012), Impact of Customer Relationship Management of Hotel (A Case study Umaid Bhwan), Volume No - 4, Issue No - 1, Issue No - 2, Page No – 130
2. Ambardar A. (2013), Understanding the importance of training practices in Indian independent hotels, Volume No - 1, Issue No - 2, Page No
3. Bagri S.C., Babu S., Kukreti M. and Smith S. (2012), Human Capital Decisions and Employee Satisfaction at Selected Hotels in India, Volume No - 29, Issue No - 2, Page No - 108.
4. Banu. S. (2012), Emerging trends in Tourism Marketing with special reference to Karnataka as Tourism Destination. Volume No -1, Issue No - 2, Page No - 22,23.
5. Bhatia A. (2013), Swot analysis of indian tourism industry, Volume No - 2, Issue No - 12, Page No - 49
6. Jain D. (2013), Visitors' Perception of Destination Image – A Case Study of J&K Tourism, Volume 2, Issue No - 1, Page No - 110,111.
7. Kalaskar P. (2013), Marketing Strategies for Standalone Hotels: With Reference to MayurAaditya Resort, Dharwad, India, Volume No - 2, Issue No - 2, Page No - 14.
8. Mathai R. (2014), Impact of Robust Technology Training through E-Learning in Corporate Hotels in India, Volume No - 6 , Issue No - 3, Page No - 166.
9. Naveed M. (2012) Customer Relationship Management in Hospitality Sector, Volume No - 1, Issue No - 1, ppg Page No - 46.
10. Singh S., Kumar D. and Sharma N. (2012), Marriott India: Managing Its Hospitality through Gearing Service Quality, Volume No - 3, Issue No - 2, Page No - 89.
11. Valdani E. *Cliente& Service Management*, Egea, Milan, 2009.
12. Manish D , K Mahesh, V Sanjeev. (2012). Online retailing in India: Opportunities and challenges. *International journal of Engineering and management sciences* 3 (3), 336-338.
13. Sharma A, Dwivedi M, L Sharma, V Sharma. (2022), Social Media Influencers: Present Scenario and the Road Ahead, *Mathematical Statistician and Engineering Applications* 71 (3), 13.

14. Dwivedi M, A Sharma. (2022). A Critical Evaluation of Customer Perception towards Online Marketing: with Special Reference to the state of Rajasthan International Journal of Early childhood Special Education 14 (2), 7106-7112
15. Dwivedi M, S Verma, JP Pathak. (2010). Linear Programming approach for identification of Industrial Location, International Journal of Engineering & Management Sciences 1 (1), 83-86.
16. Mintel, (2013) The Impact of Social Media on Tourism- International, www.store.mintel.com
17. Statista (2015) How Important Do You Think Social Media Will Be In 5 Years“ Time? www.statista.com
18. (Sirakaya & Woodside, 2005) Building and Testing Theories of Decision Making by Travelers. Tour. Manage. 26(6): 815-832
19. Fotis, Buhalis and Rossides (2011) Social media impact on holiday travel planning: The case of the Russian and the FSU markets. International Journal of Online Marketing, 1(4), 1-19.
20. de Souza, S.C. & Machado, D.F.C. (2017). Use and Influence of Social Media on Trip Planning: a quantitative study. Revista Turismo Em Análise, 28(2), 254-270.
21. Di Pietro, L. & Di Virgilio, F. (2012). Social network for the choice of tourist destination; attitude and behaviour intention. Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology, 3(1), 60- 76.
22. Dwityas, N.A. & Briandana, R. (2017). Social media in travel decision making process. International Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences, 7(7), 193-201.
23. Hamid, Z.A., Wee, H. & Hamafiah, H.M. (2016). The effect of social media on tourist`s decision to travel to Islamic destinations. A case of Malaysia. Heritage, Culture & Society Conference proceedings. Malaysia.